

Legal regulation of domain name protection

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Annotation

This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the legal regulation of the protection of domain names from cybersquatting in Uzbekistan. The current regulations, as well as judicial practice in cases of cybersquatting, are considered. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of the effectiveness of existing legal protection mechanisms and proposals for their improvement.

Key words: cyber, cybersquatting, Internet, domain names, protection, cybersecurity.

The age of rapid technological development dictates its conditions. The Internet, having firmly entered our lives, has transformed not only methods of communication, but also the very way of life. And the Internet is erasing boundaries, making information accessible to people around the world. Communication, education, business - all these areas are actively exploring the online space. The unprecedented scale and speed of information dissemination requires new approaches to its regulation.

The rapid development of the online environment requires clear legal standards that ensure the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of all participants. Websites, domain names, content, personal data - all these elements need legal protection. Fraud, data theft, distribution of malware - these and other threats require coordinated work of law enforcement agencies and international cooperation.

Recently, cases of "hijacking" of domains coinciding with the names of celebrities, trademarks and other well-known brands have become more frequent, and the resulting conflicts have led legal scholars to consider a domain name a special object of intellectual property, and to recognize cases of illegal use of domain names as unfair competition .

Cybersquatting is the registration of domain names containing a trademark, trade name or commercial designation belonging to another person for the purpose of their further resale or unfair use. People who practice such actions are called cybersquatters ¹.

In Uzbekistan, cybersquatting is a serious problem that can harm both the owners of legal intellectual property rights and bona fide Internet users. The current legislation of Uzbekistan in the field of protecting domain names from cybersquatting is regulated by The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which contains general rules on the protection of intellectual property, including trademarks.

Cybersquatting is a serious problem that requires a comprehensive solution. Judicial practice in cases of cybersquatting in Uzbekistan is not yet extensive. At the same time, there are already precedents when courts have recognized the registration of domain names that are identical or similar to someone else's trademarks as an act of cybersquatting. For example, in one of the cases, the court recognized that the registration of a domain name identical to the Samsung trademark was cybersquatting, and ordered the registrar of this domain name to transfer it to the rightful owner.

The rapid development of information and communication technologies (ICT) throughout the world, including Uzbekistan, has necessitated the legal regulation of new social relations emerging in the online environment. In response to these challenges, a number of new laws were adopted in Uzbekistan aimed at: protecting the rights and legitimate interests of:

1. Law "On Electronic Digital Signature" of December 11, 2003;
2. Law "On Electronic Commerce" of April 29, 2004;
3. Law "On Electronic Document Management" of April 29, 2004.

The adoption of progressive laws is, of course, an important step in regulating "network relations". However, this task cannot be solved solely through them. It is also necessary to review and adapt to the new reality existing laws and regulations governing traditional social relations.

The Regulations on the Procedure for Registration and Use of Domain Names in the Uz Domain (Reg. No. 1830 dated June 23, 2008) prohibits the use of a domain name for the purposes of cybersquatting and domain grabbing. However, this

¹<https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>

provision has some ambiguities. According to paragraph 75 of the Regulations, “it is prohibited to register domains for resale.” But does this norm have a legal basis?

By-laws, such as the Regulations in question, play an important role in enforcing laws. They specify and comment on legal provisions, making them more understandable and applicable in practice.

However, in this case, a problem arises: not a single law of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains a direct ban on the sale or resale of domain names. This means that the prohibition established in the Regulations does not have a solid legal basis. Due to the lack of specific legislation in this area, the ban on the resale of domain names is controversial. It may be invalidated by a court because it cannot be directly derived from existing laws. Probably, the authors of the Regulation wanted to protect the rights of third parties by prohibiting speculation in domain names. However, their intentions cannot fill the gaps in the legislation. In order to make the regulation of the resale of domain names more effective and legal, it is necessary to clarify this rule.

Global legal practice shows that a domain name can coincide with a trademark, company name, name of an individual, names of cities, films and other works. It is the rights of other persons to all of the above objects that can be violated when registering and using a domain name. Fair competition rules are often violated in this area. It doesn't matter whether the domain name is registered for resale or for your own use.

Article 177 of the Administrative Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for liability for the illegal use of someone else's trademark, service mark, geographical indication, appellation of origin of goods or confusingly similar designations for homogeneous goods (services) or illegal use of someone else's company name by imposing a fine of fifteen up to thirty basic calculated values with confiscation of the items of the offense. If the same offenses committed repeatedly within a year after the application of an administrative penalty entail a fine of thirty to fifty basic calculated amounts with confiscation of the items of the offense ².

However, this provision, firstly, does not specifically indicate liability for the illegal use of a domain name, since the purpose of using a domain name in many cases differs from the illegal use of a business name or trademark.

Since, cybersquatting is, in simple words, a type of entrepreneurial activity. His goal: to be the first to find a domain that someone potentially needs, register it

²<https://www.lex.uz/acts/97661>

in his name for a standard symbolic cost, and then resell it at a much more profitable price³.

It is also prohibited to use a domain name solely for the purpose of transferring it to a specific third party if such an action is caused by the applicant's selfish intention, aimed at obtaining a benefit, calculated on the potential interest of a third party or other potentially interested party.

An example of such actions is the registration of the domain humoair.uz in 2020 by unknown persons on the day when the creation of the airline Humo Air was announced⁴.

According to Art. 12¹ of the Law “ On Trade Names of the Republic of Uzbekistan ”, illegal use of a trade name entails a fine on legal entities from one hundred to two hundred basic calculation amounts. The amount of fines is determined for each type of offense separately⁵.

This the article does not contain any rules regarding the registration, use or protection of domain names. Accordingly, it should not apply to cases of illegal use of someone else's business name or trademark in a domain name.

In Uzbekistan, today there is a need both for the introduction of a legal institution for the protection of domain names, and for the legal regulation of issues of registration and administration of domains. The right to a domain name serves as a means of individualizing a network resource; it is unique and has independent information content; intangible, but has a number of properties that allow it to be distinguished. The introduction of a special institution for the protection of domain names will make it possible to identify a group of domains that correspond to the characteristics of an intellectual property object. Providing protection to domain names should be based on the same principles on which protection is provided to trademarks, of which the domain name should become a separate type⁶.

Despite the existence of legislation regulating the protection of domain names from cybersquatting, there are still problems in this area. Many trademark owners are not aware of their rights and how to protect their domain names from cybersquatters. It may be difficult for a trademark owner to prove that registering a

³ <https://securitymedia.org/info/tvoy-domen-moy-domen-kak-zashchititsya-ot-kiberskvottinga.html>

⁴ <https://www.spot.uz/ru/2021/04/03/cybersquatting/>

⁵ <https://lex.uz/docs/1055631>

⁶ Л.М. Бурханова. Защита средств индивидуализации в сетях интернет посредством доменных имен. Правовая защита интеллектуальной собственности: проблемы теории и практики : материалы междунар. науч.-практ. конф. 17–18 мая 2019 г. / редкол.: В. А. Богоненко (отв. ред.), Н. А. Бесецкая, И. В. Вегера. – Новополюцк : Полоц. гос. ун-т, 2019. – 43-47 с.

domain name is an act of cybersquatting. Resolving cybersquatting disputes through litigation can be lengthy and expensive.

To improve the legal regulation of protecting domain names from cybersquatting in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to inform trademark owners about their rights and how to protect their domain names from cybersquatters. Introduce administrative liability for cybersquatting. This will make it possible to more effectively combat cybersquatting without resorting to lengthy and expensive legal proceedings.

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